

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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THE DEVELOPMENT OF A PROTOCOL TO OFFER NITROUS OXIDE IN LABOR

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Pain management in labor and delivery is challenging. The current literature supports the practice of administering an epidural for complete pain relief followed by intravenous opioids as an alternative. The use of either of these two modalities can result in a negative response for both the woman and her newborn. Adverse effects range from newborn respiratory depression to prolonged second stage of labor possibly resulting in operative delivery for the woman. Nitrous oxide has been deemed a safe anxiolytic, anesthetic, and analgesic option. At a large community hospital in Southern California, nitrous oxide has not been part of the routine care. This DNP project was the development of a protocol for implementing nitrous oxide for laboring women to ensure pain relief and a better birth experience.

Keywords: nitrous oxide, pain management, satisfaction

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Background

Pain is highly subjective, and the experience of labor pain varies among women (ACNM, 2010). There are a variety of measures to relieve pain associated with labor. Common pharmacologic choices for pain relief in labor include narcotic administration via intravenous route and epidural anesthesia, with epidural anesthesia providing complete pain relief (Houser et al., 2019). Women and neonates may be exposed to risks with these pain management options. The neonate may suffer respiratory depression while the woman may experience inadequate pain relief with intravenous narcotic administration (Sanders & Lamb, 2014). An epidural may result in activity restrictions and the patient may have a hard time repositioning herself in bed, causing her an increased risk of additional interventions such as a cesarean delivery (Houser et al., 2019). Furthermore, limiting birth positions is a concern for preventing dislodgement of the epidural anesthesia catheters (Collins, 2015).

An alternative to intravenous narcotic medication or epidural anesthesia is Nitrous Oxide (N₂O). For more than 150 years, the inhalational agent N₂O has been used for its versatile properties of anxiolytic, anesthesia, and analgesia (Collins et al., 2018). The use of N₂O is common in Europe but has not been as widely used in the U.S. (Collins et al., 2018). One factor that may account for the limited use is that clinicians may not see this option as a practical tool that can be used in labor and delivery (Collins, 2017). N₂O has several characteristics that make it an appropriate analgesic for use in labor (Collins et al., 2018). N₂O has a quick effect and is rapidly eliminated in approximately 30 seconds after the woman stops using it (King & Wong, 2014). Additionally, N₂O does not affect the contractility of the uterus, the neonate heartbeat, Apgar scores, or need for resuscitation of the neonate (Migliaccio et al., 2017). N₂O is intended to create a disassociation from the acuity of pain, as well as have an anxiolytic result (Houser et

al., 2019). The patient must remain awake and alert and be able to control the inhalation mask for N₂O administration, without loss of motor or sensory function. Subsequently, the patient-controlled features promote a sense of empowerment for women (Collins et al., 2018). A practice bulletin was released in 2017 by the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG) that supported N₂O use and cited benefits, such as the ability to stay mobile in labor, not needing additional monitoring of the neonate, and the patient's ability to use as needed (ACOG, 2017).

Local Context

This Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project will take place in a 262 licensed-bed community hospital in Anaheim, California, that has a labor and delivery unit that averages 315 deliveries a month. A multidisciplinary approach is used in this unit by staff members consisting of labor and delivery nurses, certified nurse-midwives, and obstetricians. The unit is also supported by an anesthesiologist, surgical technician, neonatologist, neonatal intensive care unit nurses, and respiratory therapists. When asked about their pain management plan, 45% of women admitted for labor planned on having epidural anesthesia for pain management. Women who wanted intravenous pain medication or nothing at all wanted to be able to ambulate, shower and have music and/or aromatherapy to help them cope with the pain. There are some women who have contraindication to either epidural anesthesia or intravenous opioid analgesia. For example, women with gestational thrombocytopenia are not able to receive epidural anesthesia (Vallejo & Zakowski, 2019). Likewise, women with a history of drug use are discouraged to use or decline intravenous opioid analgesia (Migliaccio et al., 2017). However, based on clinical observation, many women in this community hospital desire minimal to no interventions during labor regarding pain management because of their effect on the woman and her neonate.

Attempting to help manage labor pain and the anxiety that is associated with it becomes a challenge to the clinician. Nitrous oxide has not been used in this facility but would be an excellent addition to the pain management options.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor in Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to develop a protocol for nitrous oxide use as a pain management option for laboring women who are opposed to or have contraindications to epidural anesthesia or intravenous opioid analgesia.

Supporting Framework

A framework is an outline that guides the development of the study allowing the investigator to associate findings to nursing's body of knowledge (Grove & Gray, 2019). This DNP project used The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care as a guiding framework (see Figure 1). First developed in 1994 by a group of nurses from the University of Iowa Hospital and Clinics and the College of Nursing, this model is used to guide clinicians in evaluating and using research discoveries to support patient care (Titler et al., 1994; Godshell, 2019). The Iowa Model is frequently used as the basis for evidence-based practice (EBP) initiatives to use current best evidence for practice (Godshell, 2019). Successful projects using this model have resulted in practice changes in baby to mother bonding (Boyd, 2017), mental health emergency response teams (Loucks et al., 2010) and education programs offered to nurses in military medical treatment facilities (Titler & Moore, 2010).

Figure 1

The Iowa Model for Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

Identifying Triggering Issues and Opportunities

According to Titler et al., (1994), the first step in the Iowa Model is to identify either a problem-focused trigger or a knowledge-focused trigger where an EBP change may be needed. Triggers that are problem-focused result from risk management data, financial data, or the identification of a medical problem. Triggers that are knowledge-focused are recognized when new research discoveries are presented or the requirement for new practice guidelines is evident.

Stating the Problem

The problem statement is then developed using the PICOT acronym that stands for population (who is the focus of your study or project); intervention (what action/conduct is being tested); comparison (who are you comparing your population to); outcome (what are the results you are investigating); and time (what is the length of the intervention or study period) (Roush, 2019).

Determining if the Issue is a Priority

The second step of this framework is to identify whether the problem is a priority for the organization or unit. Problems with higher volume or costs will more than likely be a priority for the organization, which can affect organizational buy-in. Current evidence shows that N₂O is a cost-effective pain management option for patients who want pain relief but are opposed/unable to have epidural anesthesia or intravenous opioid analgesia. According to the literature, training the labor and delivery nurses on how to initiate N₂O administration has been done during their regularly scheduled shifts keeping costs at a minimum (Migliaccio et al., 2017).

Forming a Team

The third step is to develop a team with key members that include key interdisciplinary stakeholders that will aid in the development, evaluation, and implementation of the change.

The proposed interdisciplinary team members for this DNP project included the clinical nurse specialist, a certified nurse-midwife, anesthesiologist, pharmacist, obstetrician, nurse manager and at least two labor and delivery nurses.

Assemblage, Appraising, and Synthesizing the Evidence

The fourth step of this model is to gather, and analysis EBP research associated to the desired practice outcome. Once the project purpose was identified, the team conducted a literature search that pertained to the project purpose. The team then critiqued the available studies to identify strengths and limitations and to determine if there was sufficient research to support the implementation of a practice change. The following criteria was considered: reliable conclusions exist from a sufficient number of studies to support the change; the type and value of the studies; the clinical significance of the findings; the number of studies with comparable sample features; the viability of the findings in practice; and the risk-benefit ratio. Once the standards were met, the team designed an action plan to implement the intervention as a test practice change (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017).

Designing and Piloting the Practice Change

The last phase was an assessment of the application, to safeguard the change was achievable and would result in enhanced outcomes before full-scale execution (Brown, 2014). Once the pilot implementation of the intervention was successful, the team then proceeded with the organizational practice change. The team would then continue to assess the practice modification and conduct evaluation for any deviation in practice or a decline in the anticipated results.

The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care is the framework that guided the development of this DNP project as a problem-focused problem was evident and

a new practice guideline was needed to offer laboring women additional options for pain management. Uterine contractions and cervical opening results in crude pain (T-10 through L-1). Also, as labor advances, the descent of the fetal head followed by pressure on the pelvic floor, vagina, and perineum produce somatic pain conveyed by the pudendal nerve (S2-4) (ACOG, 2002). Laboring women who want drug/anesthesia free intervention and/or have a contraindication to epidural or intravenous opioid analgesia have no other option but to try to manage the pain. This theoretical framework is designed to enable Certified Nurse-Midwives and nurses to question present practices and to explore whether care can be enhanced using up-to-date research answers.

Review of Literature

A literature review was completed by utilizing the following databases: PubMed, Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL)/EBSCO and Science Direct. Keyword search terms included "nitrous oxide," "Entonox," "labor," "pain relief," "anxiolytic effect," "management of pain" and "satisfaction."

Table 1

PubMed

Terms	Limiters	Articles retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles reviewed	Articles used
Nitrous oxide AND labor	Peer-reviewed, English, publication date: 2010-2020	56	39	17	15
Nitrous oxide AND anxiolytic AND labor	Peer-reviewed, English, publication date: 2015-2020	4	2	2	2

Table 2

Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Database Search/EBSCO

Terms	Limiters	Articles retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles reviewed	Articles used
Nitrous oxide AND labor AND pain relief	Peer-reviewed, English, publication date: 2010-2020	2	0	2	1
Entonox AND labor AND pain relief	Peer-reviewed, English, publication date: 2010-2020	7	0	7	2
Nitrous oxide in labor AND pain relief	Peer-reviewed, English, publication date: 2010-2020	4	0	4	2
Nitrous oxide for the management of labor	Peer-reviewed, English, publication date: 2010-2020	2	0	1	1

Table 3*Science Direct*

Terms	Limiters	Articles retrieved	Articles excluded	Articles reviewed	Articles used
Nitrous oxide AND pain relief AND satisfaction	Peer-reviewed, English, publication date: 2015-2020	7	5	2	0
Nitrous oxide AND pain relief AND labor	Peer-reviewed, English, publication date: 2015-2020	5	1	4	0

Delimitations were 2010 to the present, peer-reviewed journals, and English language only. The use of two position statements were included from the American College of Nurse-Midwives (2010) and the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. Both sources are leading authorities that govern the practice of labor and delivery and the management of women's health throughout their lifespans. The search yielded 87 articles. These were further examined but 33 were eliminated because they were quality improvement projects, updates, editorials or repeat articles. Twenty-two articles were utilized for this DNP project. These studies included gravid women in labor planning a vaginal birth and using N₂O for pain management.

The following review of literature discusses the mechanism of action for N₂O, how N₂O is used for the laboring woman, and uses for N₂O other than during delivery. The review also includes a comparison of N₂O use with epidural analgesia, and opioid analgesia and the side effects and contraindications to N₂O. A discussion of occupational exposure is addressed and finally, studies examining maternal satisfaction are presented.

Nitrous Oxide

An inhalational agent that has been used for more than 150 years, N₂O has anesthetic, analgesic, and anxiolytic properties (Collins et al., 2018). The exact mechanism of action for N₂O remains uncertain (Likis et al., 2014; Collins, 2015; Klomp et al., 2012; Collins et al., 2018). According to Collins (2015), the main theory is that N₂O prevents excitatory glutamatergic neurotransmission via non-competitive inhibition of the N-Methyl-D-aspartic acid (NMDA) subtype of glutamine receptors. It is perceived that the mechanism of N₂O may be by stimulation of endogenous opioid release. The analgesic result occurs by opioid peptide release in the brain stem, which then arouses the descending noradrenergic inhibitory neurons, diminishing the processing of pain impulses in the spinal cord (Klomp et al., 2012; Collins, 2015; Collins et al., 2018). The anxiolytic effect may be especially useful in laboring women by permitting them to have a sense of control with the ability to self-administer and possibly avoid an invasive procedure such as insertion of an intravenous catheter that is not needed with N₂O use (Collins, 2015; Zairova et al., 2018; Buhre et al., 2019; & Agah et al., 2014). N₂O has been used in different healthcare settings and situations such as dentistry, intravenous cannulation placement, and laceration repair in children because of its anxiolytic properties (Collins, 2017).

Management of Nitrous Oxide in Labor and Delivery

Inhaled N₂O is an attractive pain management option in labor and delivery because it has a fast onset of effect and a short half-life (Houser et al., 2019; King & Wong, 2014; Collins, 2015; Collins et al., 2018). Within 30 seconds after it is discontinued, N₂O is eliminated from the body in its original form completely by the lungs (King & Wong, 2014). An odorless, tasteless, nonflammable gas, N₂O is composed of two nitrogen atoms and one oxygen atom stored in pressurized gas cylinders under its critical temperature where it exists concurrently in

gas and liquid phases (Collins et al., 2018). The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) permits the use in labor and delivery with intermittent flow of N₂O to the patient in a 50/50 blend of nitrous oxide and oxygen (Collins, 2017). The flow of N₂O is introduced only after the laboring woman has made an acceptable seal of the mask around her mouth and nose or has closed her lips around the mouthpiece and then breathes in deeply. When the patient breathes in, negative pressure causes a demand valve in the device to open which permits the gas to flow into the mask/mouthpiece of the patient. When the patient exhales, the demand valve closes, stopping the gas flow. The gas flow is not reinitiated until the next inhalation. For the best effect, each woman must be taught to begin inhaling about 30 seconds prior to the beginning of a contraction because the start of action takes about 30 seconds. Analgesic effects happen in 50 seconds and for some women, it can take three to four contractions to acquire the technique and timing (Collins, 2017; Houser et al., 2019). For safety, it is important that the laboring woman is the only one allowed to hold the mask/mouthpiece. Intravenous (IV) access is not necessary for the sole use of N₂O because medications are not required to reverse the result of N₂O. If there is no relief or the patient is unhappy with N₂O, she simply stops inhaling through the mask or mouthpiece and the gas is excreted within minutes through the lung tissue (King & Wong, 2014). The literature states N₂O does not protract labor, disturb uterine activity, or cause any changes in fetal heart rate; therefore, it is not necessary to do continuous fetal monitoring, allowing for ambulation without restrictions (Agah et al., 2014; Collins, 2015; Collins, 2017; Collins et al., 2018; Klomp et al., 2012; Likis et al., 2014).

Nitrous Oxide Use Beyond Delivery

N₂O has been effectively used for other purposes besides the first and second stage of labor (pushing, vacuum, or forceps assisted vaginal deliveries). It is predominantly helpful for

women undergoing rapid labor with imminent delivery, transition, and second-stage labor (Richardson et al., 2018). It may also be used in the third stage with postdelivery procedures such as laceration or episiotomy repair, manual extraction of the placenta and uterine curettage (Berlit et al., 2013). Studies have documented effectiveness for women waiting for regional anesthesia, adjunct therapy to regional anesthesia that is not functioning well, external cephalic version, painful vaginal exam, insertion of intracervical Foley bulb or laminaria for cervical ripening and induction of labor, and intrauterine monitor insertions during labor to assess uterine contraction patterns and fetal well-being (Agah et al., 2014; Berlit et al., 2013; Buhre et al., 2019; Likis et al., 2014; Collins, 2017; Sutton et al., 2017).

Comparison of Nitrous Oxide with Other Agents

Epidural Analgesia

Epidural anesthesia is the gold standard for complete pain relief in labor. However, there are disadvantages to using epidural anesthesia which include protraction of labor; requirement of oxytocin; assisted vaginal birth, such as with forceps or vacuum; maternal hypotension; and urinary retention (Agah et al., 2014; Sutton et al., 2017). With N₂O, there are no blocked motor nerves that prevent ambulation during labor (ACOG, 2017). Additionally, with epidural analgesia, the inability to move leads to maternal exhaustion and hindrance of fetal descent during labor decreasing pushing force causing prolonged labor (Agah et al., 2014; Collins, 2017).

Opioid analgesia

Most obstetric units in advanced countries offer intramuscular, intravenous or a combination of the two routes of opioids for pain management. The most common opioids used are morphine, nalbupine and fentanyl. Studies show that laboring women preferred opioid

analgesia over N₂O because of immediate pain relief (Jones et al., 2012; Klomp et al., 2012).

However, there are apprehensions about the effects of opioid analgesia on the patient as there is a decreased capacity to participate in decision making about care, sedation, hypoventilation, hypotension, prolonged labor, urine retention, nausea/vomiting, and the reducing of gastric emptying which increases the risk of inhalation of gastric contents if general anesthesia is mandatory in an emergency (Klomp et al., 2012). Similarly, there are concerns for the fetus because opioids easily cross the placenta by passive diffusion and have negatively affected fetal heart rate patterns during labor (Klomp et al., 2012; Likis et al., 2014). Hence, the laboring woman is required to have constant fetal monitoring to assess fetal well-being during labor. Major concerns for the neonate are hypothermia and respiratory depression as well as delayed ineffective breastfeeding due to decreased alertness and inhibited suckling at the breast (Jones et al., 2012; Klomp et al., 2012; Likis et al., 2014; Parsa et al., 2017). There has been a rise in the proportion of gravid women actively using heroin, prescription opioids, or on methadone treatment for opioid disorders in the last ten years, which predisposes them to ineffective pharmacologic pain management (Migliaccio et al., 2017). Women who have an addiction problem may also have had a history of sexual trauma; therefore, meeting the criteria for posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and possibly benefitting from the anxiolytic effect of N₂O (Migliaccio et al., 2017).

Nitrous Oxide Side Effects and Contraindications

Potential side effects of N₂O include nausea, vomiting, and the loss of consciousness if too much gas is inhaled (Collins et al., 2018). Loss of consciousness is extremely rare because of the FDA approval of a 50/50 blend of N₂O and oxygen (compared to previous concentrations of 75% to 100%) (Collins, 2015). There are cases where the loss of consciousness occurs when

N₂O is not self-administered but is quickly resolved with a breath or two of room air or oxygen (Klomp et al., 2012). There is also the potential for aspiration of stomach contents produced by loss of the protective laryngeal reflexes while unconscious (Collins, 2015). Other side effects include confusion, lightheadedness, dehydration, or tingling of the extremities; although some of the side effects such as nausea, vomiting, disorientation and vertigo can naturally occur in laboring women (Klomp et al., 2012; Houser et al., 2019; King & Wong, 2014; Buhre et al., 2019; Collins, 2015; Rooks, 2011).

N₂O use is contraindicated for some patients. Situations that may produce space for the collection of gas such as a pneumothorax, increased intraocular pressure, intracranial pressure and inner ear surgery preclude N₂O use (Collins, 2018). Additionally, low Vit B12 as seen in diseases like celiac spruce, pernicious anemia, Crohn's disease, and gastric bypass surgery preclude N₂O use, because N₂O can lead to the repression of methionine synthase production, which can result in megaloblastic anemia in these people (Rooks, 2011). Other contraindications include impaired consciousness, whether by medication, drug and alcohol use, injury or functional impairments that limit the use of the woman's extremities (Collins, 2017; Collins, 2018; Collins et al., 2018; Likis et al., 2014).

Occupational Hazards Associated with the Use of Nitrous Oxide

Collins et al. (2018), found that dental hygienists with a workplace exposure to N₂O were more likely to experience infertility, preterm labor, and spontaneous abortions. These healthcare workers had higher risk of exposure than that associated with labor and delivery use due to a closer proximity to the source. Possible risk to professional healthcare personnel regularly exposed to N₂O has led to the introduction of occupational exposure limits (OEL) (Magliaccio et al., 2017; Rooks, 2011). Exposure to even a small amount of gas in the workplace is expressed

as a health based OEL. The OEL for N₂O is restricted to an 8-hour, time-weighted average (8-h TWA) concentration of 25 parts per million. In countries like the United Kingdom, Italy, Sweden, Norway, and Denmark, the OEL for N₂O is limited up to 100 parts per million. The 25 parts per million allowed in the United States was set in 1970 by the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health to ensure precautions for U.S. healthcare workers (Collins et al., 2018; Collins, 2018; Vallejo & Zakowski, 2019; King & Wong, 2014; Likis et al., 2014).

The FDA approved a delivery apparatus containing scavenger devices that collect the exhaled gas particles that the patient exhales into the mask or mouthpiece and directs the exhaled gas to a waste reservoir where suitable discarding is obtained (Collins, 2017). A scavenging system is the only dedicated equipment mandated to minimize contact and risk to healthcare workers and others present. The system has 3 major components: positive pressure relief, negative pressure relief, and a reservoir. Positive pressure relief safeguards the equipment and patient from threats that are likely to occur in events such as occlusion. Excessive flow of gas is diverted into the reservoir avoiding release into the adjacent environment. A negative pressure relief valve stops the creation of a vacuum where flow rate is too low (Collins, 2017).

Maternal Satisfaction and Nitrous Oxide

It is generally known that pain is associated with labor and birth (Roberts et al., 2010). The International Association of the Study of Pain and the American Pain Society has defined pain as an unpleasant physical and emotional experience related to actual or potential tissue damage (Merskey, 1979). Pain relief in labor and birth is essential for some women, but others place a higher precedence on other aspects of the birth experience. Richardson et al. (2017), used a large database of a consistent postdelivery survey given to women who delivered from 2011-2014. They investigated the patterns associated with N₂O. Pain relief by neuraxial

analgesia was generally excellent and satisfaction was consistently high. Pain relief from N₂O was inconsistent, mostly indicating only mild-to-moderate analgesic effectiveness. In another study, Richardson et al. (2018), conducted a qualitative content analysis of comments documented during normal postpartum follow-up of women who delivered vaginally and had used N₂O as their sole labor analgesic. Their study identified six major themes. Incomplete, partial, or transient analgesia was the first theme; the way women described their pain relief, yet they stated that they were satisfied. The second theme was that non-analgesic effects enhanced coping by distracting the woman from pain and redirecting their focus to their breathing. Women also stated that they had an anxiolytic effect, and that this promoted relaxation and dissociation from pain. The third theme was consistency with their birth plan, as N₂O was helpful in attaining normal childbirth, especially for those women who delivered imminently. The fourth theme was dealings between patient and device use where women had a diminished experience due to technical issues with apparatus. Side effects experienced with the use of N₂O was the fifth theme. Women acknowledged that these were insignificant. Finally, the sixth theme was “superlatives” highlighting the effect of N₂O. For example, some women commented that they “could not have done it without N₂O.”

The findings from this study highlight the satisfaction obtained from the use of N₂O even without experiencing complete pain relief. Improved satisfaction with individual birth experiences is possible if women are given the information to make the right choices in their care (King & Wong, 2014; Houser et al., 2019; Parsa et al., 2017; Sheyklo et al., 2017). Therefore, a more applicable measure of success is satisfaction instead of pain assessment because N₂O is not proposed to provide complete relief of pain (Berlit et al., 2013; Likis et al., 2014; King & Wong, 2014; Sheyklo et al., 2017).

In summary, the literature has shown that N₂O is safe and can be effectively used in labor and delivery to provide women with another option for pain relief during their birthing experience. The invaluable combination of the effects of inhaled N₂O are both analgesic and anxiolytic and can be beneficial and safe in all three phases of labor (Collins et al., 2018).

Methods

The objective for this project was to develop a nursing protocol for the administration of N₂O to women in labor. The protocol that was developed consists of criteria and process. The training plan accompanying the protocol includes evidenced-based strategies to help increase nurses' knowledge and comfort in using N₂O for alleviating labor pain. This section contains information about the protocol development, a description of the population, and facility where the protocol will be implemented. The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care provided the structure needed to develop the protocol.

Setting

The setting for this DNP project was the labor and delivery unit at a private teaching hospital with a 262 licensed bed capacity in Anaheim, California. The hospital has a busy labor and delivery unit that averages about 315 deliveries a month. The unit is staffed with three physicians, a Certified Nurse Midwife (CNM), and labor and delivery nurses. Sixty percent of the deliveries are attended by CNMs. The unit is also supported by an anesthesiologist, surgical technician, neonatologist, respiratory therapists, neonatal intensive care nurses and phlebotomists. In this setting, women in labor currently have two pharmacological options for pain management. They can choose between IV opioid analgesia or epidural analgesia.

Population of Interest

The protocol was developed for women in labor wanting additional options for pain management or who have contraindications to opioid and/or epidural analgesia. Women who are eligible for N₂O included those who are full-term, low risk, and have a singleton in vertex position. Women who have diet controlled gestational diabetes and women with gestational thrombocytopenia are also potential candidates for N₂O. Desired outcomes of the protocol

implementation include patient satisfaction with N₂O analgesia and the overall birth experience. Women are not eligible for N₂O if they have multiple gestation, malposition, insulin dependent diabetes, a history of pneumothorax, increased ocular pressure, intracranial pressure, inner ear surgery, low vitamin B12 (associated with celiac sprue disease), Crohn's disease, pernicious anemia and gastric bypass surgery (Collins, 2017; Collins, 2018; Collins et al., 2018; Likis et al., 2014). All of the criteria listed above were included in the protocol.

Ethical Considerations

Since the purpose of this DNP project was to develop a protocol that would be ready for implementation, no human subjects were involved. Patient, family, or staff data were not collected. This protocol development project was exempt from IRB review for California State University, Fullerton (CSUF).

Procedures

The first step of the Iowa Model was to detect triggering issues or opportunities. In labor and delivery, where pain is experienced by all women in varying degrees, offering N₂O is an additional choice for managing pain and satisfaction. The problem or triggering issue identified was that women who have a contraindication to epidural anesthesia and did not want to take opioids for pain management, did not have another option for pain management during labor. Addressing a woman's pain in labor as well as her satisfaction with the birth experience was a priority which was addressed by the second step of the Iowa Model that asks if the problem was a priority.

The third step was to form a multidisciplinary team. This team involved the clinical experts who reviewed drafts of the protocol. Clinical experts were defined in the proposal as

clinicians and educators who had worked with N₂O, whether administering/educating the patient or implementing the use of N₂O in their work setting.

A review of literature was the fourth step. In this DNP project, a review involved collecting and evaluating clinical evidence related to the project and desired outcome. The literature that was reviewed helped in the formation of the protocol for nurses to follow regarding eligibility of N₂O use, contraindications and possible adverse effects, and the preparation and administration of N₂O. Resources, such as other hospital protocols for N₂O administration, were obtained as well as clinical practice guidelines published by other facilities and ACNM/ACOG.

The fifth step of the Iowa Model was to pilot the implementation of the intervention to ensure feasibility and to examine outcomes. The pilot and actual implementation of the use of N₂O in labor will occur after the completion of this DNP program. The current pandemic of COVID-19 deemed it impossible to allow any new projects such as this quality improvement project in the current facility. It is hopeful that once a vaccine is available and the pandemic is under control, the facility can proceed in the process of securing N₂O. Once N₂O is present and ready for use, staff training will begin. When all staff are trained, the pilot testing will begin. A formal evaluation will be conducted to assess if patient outcomes have improved, stayed the same, or worsened.

Steps in Developing the Protocol

Current evidence and professional guidelines were used, and in collaboration with a panel of experts (described below) with experience in obstetrics, anesthesia and labor and delivery, the project director (PD) developed the protocol to offer N₂O to laboring women on the labor and delivery unit of the community hospital. The protocol delineated the criteria for N₂O

administration, process of administration, and training and evaluation of administering personnel. The PD currently works as a CNM in a full scope practice in Orange County and serves as a preceptor for student nurse midwives.

Expert Panel

The first expert was a clinical nurse specialist, with over 10 years' experience in the role of Parent-Child Clinical Nurse Specialist, Perinatal Services – Labor and Delivery, Postpartum. She is a graduate of California State University, Los Angeles (CSULA) in 2005, with a Bachelor of Science in Nursing; CSULA in 2006 with a Master of Science in Nursing – specialty in Nursing Administration; Azusa Pacific University in 2007 with a Post-Master's Certificate in Parent-Child Clinical Nurse Specialist.

The second expert was the lead anesthesiologist for the labor and delivery unit. He graduated from the University of Southern California Medical School in 1992. He completed his anesthesia residency through the University of California, Los Angeles in 1996. He has two years of private practice with Friendly Hills Medical Group and has been in his current position for 22 years.

The third expert was a Certified Nurse Midwife who currently works in Harbor City, California, in a facility that offers and uses N₂O in labor. She has been at Harbor City since 2015. She is a graduate of Columbia University in New York and received her Master of Science in Nursing in 2012. She has experience in and out of hospital practice, both in home birth and birth centers. Her current work facility obtained N₂O in 2018, and she has experience using it in birth centers as well.

The PD met with each member of the expert panel either in person, by phone, email and/or text to obtain their assistance in revision of the draft protocol.

Review of Literature

The review of literature was conducted by the PD. Articles from 2010 to current were obtained and reviewed in order to provide an evidence base for the protocol. N₂O has been primarily used outside of the United States and only articles in English were utilized (Collins, 2018; Rooks, 2011).

Most of the articles used were in the labor and delivery setting. A few of the articles referenced other settings/situations where N₂O was used because of its anxiolytic properties. These were dental procedures, intravenous cannulation placement, and laceration repair in children (Collins, 2017). Occupational hazards with the use of N₂O were described in the literature and posed a major concern for our anesthesiologist when these were discussed. The literature was consistent in stating that the use of the FDA approved scavenging capability built into all equipment used for N₂O would significantly decrease the occupational hazard exposure unlike those in dentistry where the unit was absent, exposing employees (Collins, 2018; Rooks, 2011).

According to the literature, women are eligible for N₂O if they are in active labor, or are awaiting induction of labor, have an oxygenation level of more than 95% on room air and have a normal reactive fetal heart rate tracing (Houser et al., 2019). Women undertaking any difficult procedure such as perineal laceration repair and physical removal of placenta are also candidates for N₂O (Berlit et al., 2013; Collins, 2017). A woman is not eligible for N₂O if she cannot hold her own mask, have a history of pulmonary hypertension, increased intraocular pressure, pneumothorax or increased intracranial pressure, have a documented vitamin B12 deficiency, and a history of alcohol or illegal drug use (Houser et al., 2019). All of the information from the review of literature was presented and discussed individually with the expert panel.

Committee Approval

The Perinatal Patient Safety Committee (PPS) at the site hospital, reviews and approves protocols, guidelines, policy, and procedures pertaining to labor and delivery, postpartum, infant/newborn and family. The committee currently meets every second Thursday on even months. A PowerPoint presentation was created and presented to the committee on December 10, 2020, after it was reviewed by the CSUF project lead. It was emphasized that the actual implementation would take place at a later date because of the current pandemic and its potential to spread the COVID-19 virus through aerosolization. The presentation included an introduction to the use of N₂O, background literature, and the clinical problem in the labor and delivery unit. The PPS committee was informed that the purpose of the project was to develop a protocol for N₂O as a pain management option for laboring women who are opposed to or have contraindications to epidural/intravenous opioid analgesia. The Expert Panel members were identified. The presentation also discussed the conceptual framework used that guided the procedures. The committee members were asked to consider the development of the protocol, consultation/discussion with the expert panel and feedback and changes to the protocol. The plan was to return in February with the finished protocol for review and feedback.

The committee was very receptive to the project and the nurse educator commented that the presentation was well organized and clear. The clinical nurse specialist and nurse administrator were excited about the potential of making N₂O available as soon as possible. The physician chairperson asked about going through the facility's IRB before implementation and to make sure there would be an anesthesiologist at the next meeting when the actual protocol would be presented after changes were made by the expert panel. The PPS committee approved the

request to present a protocol to offer N₂O after it was discussed and modified by the expert panel. The proposed protocol presentation was scheduled for February 11, 2020.

Draft of Protocol and Revision

A draft protocol was based upon the review of literature and given to the expert panel for review. The draft was emailed individually to each member. The CNM replied first stating that the proposed protocol was very good and thorough. She did recommend including whether the patient received IV opioids within two hours under contraindications. Her other recommendation was to use N₂O with a Category II fetal heart rate tracing. The CNS had several recommendations and clarifications that she included on her copy and then emailed back to the PD for consideration. The anesthesiologist reviewed the protocol and commented that it looked complete other than adding the use of continuous pulse oximetry while N₂O was in use by the patient. Revisions to the protocol were made according to the expert panel's input.

Committee Approval

The updated protocol was emailed to the PPSP committee chairperson to include in the dissemination of agenda and minutes so that committee members could review the protocol prior to meeting on February 11, 2020. When the protocol was discussed, the Chief of Service inquired about the cost of the scavenger unit. The scavenger unit has a cost of \$5000 and each disposable mask unit is about \$20. Discussion from the perinatologist included if N₂O had any negative effect on preterm infants, those born under 35 weeks gestation. The perinatologist also asked for the patient population to be more defined. For example, she wanted to know if asthmatic patients could use N₂O and if N₂O would have the same effect on severe obese patients with a body mass index (BMI) over 40. The PD did not have the answers to her questions but stated that she would conduct a literature review and report findings to her directly. The PPS

committee was happy with the proposed protocol but tabled it until new projects could be implemented back into the facility, especially since budget issues for the much-needed personal protective equipment (PPE) and staff shortages were still an issue during the pandemic. The PD also planned to develop educational materials for providers and staff as well as for patients and families.

Results and Final Product

The final product of this DNP project was an approved protocol for the administration of N₂O that would be ready to implement and evaluate. (See Appendix A for protocol.)

Implementation Plan

The pilot and actual implementation of the use of N₂O in labor will occur after the completion of this DNP program, as it is not within the scope of the project. Pending approval of the use of N₂O, the project director will be available the first day of implementation to identify and address any barriers. Staff will be trained to complete an eligibility form for each woman admitted to the floor. The patient eligibility form will be in the form of paper charting during the test phase and will include the following questions:

1. Is the patient eligible for N₂O?
2. Did the nurse offer N₂O to the patient for pain relief?
3. If N₂O was not offered, document reason why.
4. Was N₂O requested by the patient but not provided?
5. Why was N₂O not provided?

If the patient meets the criteria, she will be offered pain management options that include N₂O. If she selects N₂O, the nurse will obtain an order from the obstetric provider. The nurse will then obtain and document the patient's baseline oxygen saturation and vital signs. She will proceed to instruct the patient on appropriate performance of N₂O use, including holding the mask to her face, making a close-fitting seal with the mask, inhaling at the beginning of the contraction, inhaling and exhaling into the mask during the contraction, and then removing the mask to breathe room air when the contraction has ended (Houser et al., 2019). The nurse will

document when the woman started and when she stopped use of N₂O, her level of pain relief using a visual analog scale (VAS) from 0-10 and any problems. The nurse will remain in the room until the patient establishes proper technique and review with her that only she can hold her own mask. The patient's family will be educated that just the patient will hold the mask up to her face and family will not be allowed to assist in any way (Houser et al., 2019; Collins, 2017).

Staff Education

Staff education will be done by the implementation team which includes this project director, two to three labor and delivery registered nurses who have volunteered and will be the resource persons for questions, and the clinical nurse specialist. Implementation will start after going through the manufacturer training process. The implementation team will conduct a training program for registered nurses in labor and delivery on the efficacy of N₂O using the teach-back method, assess if the patient is eligible and what needs to be documented. Review of safety aspects of the N₂O system will occur as well as demonstration and use of the system. Staff involved will be given the opportunity to practice handling the equipment so that they can accurately demonstrate functionality of the system. All nurses will sign an attendance sheet to ensure that all labor and delivery nurses have handled the equipment and that all questions were answered. Written material regarding eligibility standards, patient education, and safety aspects will be developed by the implementation team which will be derived from the N₂O manufacturer and review of literature.

Plan for Evaluation

Once the protocol is in place, it is crucial to perform a formal evaluation to assess if patient outcomes have improved, stayed the same, or worsened. Three process measures will help determine project success. They include the number of eligible women to use N₂O; the number

of women offered N₂O; and the total number of women who used N₂O. Evaluation will include how frequently the patient used N₂O and for how long during the labor. Measuring women's perceptions of pain relief and satisfaction with N₂O can be done by using a VAS scale and performing individual interviews in the postdelivery period (within two hours of delivery).

Analgesia and satisfaction scores may be grouped into a score of 8 to 10 indicating high, 5 to 7 indicating intermediate, and 0 to 4 indicating low (Richardson et al., 2017). A survey to assess a woman's satisfaction will include:

- Preference for pain relief
- Satisfaction with her choice of N₂O
- Pain relief she experienced from N₂O
- The use of N₂O in addition to IV opioid and/or epidural
- Desire to use N₂O again for a future labor

Discussion

It was understood that having N₂O on site was not a priority, given the current pandemic of COVID -19 and resources, which were prioritized on PPE, staff shortages and supplies for the units. It is hopeful that N₂O will become available in the near future as many providers and nurses who have used N₂O in the past, agree that it is an effective and a good adjunct to the options of pain management. The protocol was developed based on the literature and consultation with content and clinical experts. As the protocol is implemented, there may be benefits to other patients and in other clinical situations.

A 2014 study showed that inhaled nitrous oxide has been used successfully in preterm infants for its pulmonary vasodilating effects with pulmonary hypertension (Kumar, 2014). Although N₂O has not been recommended to use in preterm infants under 34 weeks, women in preterm labor may be offered N₂O to safely manage pain and anxiety associated with preterm delivery because N₂O is eliminated from the body in its original form completely by the lungs (King & Wong, 2014; Kumar, 2014).

There were no studies found that evaluated the use of N₂O for women in labor who had a history of asthma. Brunick & Clark (2010) stated that asthma has often been seen as a contraindication for N₂O use but acknowledged that research does not substantiate this claim. Therefore, Brunick & Clark (2010) report that N₂O can be safely used for asthmatic patients.

Morbidly obese pregnant women are high risk patients because the weight of the chest wall is increased resulting in a greater work of breathing and energy expenditure in respiration. They may experience frequent shallow breathing patterns, leading to a decrease in the expiratory reserve volume (ERV), residual volume, and functional residual capacity (FRC) of the lung (Tan & Sia, 2011). Systemic opioids and N₂O have limited efficacy and have been shown to cause

airway obstruction and hypoxemia (Tan & Sia, 2011). Therefore, this category of pregnant women would not be eligible for N₂O use.

Conclusion

Pain is very subjective, and each woman experiences pain very differently. Current literature has shown that N₂O has been a safe anxiolytic, anesthetic, and analgesic option for women in labor. Many women in this community hospital desire minimal to no interventions in labor regarding pain management because of their effect on the woman and her neonate. The addition of N₂O to the option of pain management will increase a woman's birth experience autonomy and increase her overall satisfaction with her decision.

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APPENDIX A

Nitrous Oxide Protocol

Authorized Personnel: Registered Nurses in Labor and Delivery

Workplace safety message: N₂O is a known female reproductive toxin and has been associated with spontaneous abortion in health care workers. The FDA approved delivery apparatus containing a scavenger device collects the exhaled gas particles that the patient exhales into the mask/mouthpiece into a waste reservoir where suitable discarding is obtained. The scavenger system is the only dedicated equipment mandated to minimize contact and risk to healthcare workers and others present. (Collins, 2017; Collins et al., 2018).

Description:

1. Function:

To establish guidelines and procedures for the administration of N₂O as an option for pain management to women in labor by the Labor and Delivery Registered Nurse.

2. Definitions and Criteria:

2.1: Patients who are in active labor, scheduled for an induction of labor, and/or undergoing any painful procedure such as perineal repair meet criteria for the use of N₂O.

2.2: The obstetrician or the CNM on call will ensure there is an order for N₂O, once they have assessed that the patient is eligible and meets criteria. The order will be an order set in Health Connect that will include to assess the patient's vital signs, O₂ saturation, Category I/II fetal heart rate tracing, and patient's demonstration and understanding on how to self-administer. The order will be initiated by the patient care registered nurse (RN), CNM, or obstetrician.

3. Treatment Goal:

3.1: To offer woman autonomy in choosing their own pain management option in labor. A study by Richardson et al. (2018) highlighted the satisfaction obtained from the use of N₂O even without experiencing complete pain relief. The invaluable combination of the effects of inhaled N₂O are both analgesic and anxiolytic and can be beneficial and safe in all three phases of labor improving satisfaction with individual birth experiences (Collins et al., 2018; King & Wong, 2014; Houser et al., 2019).

3.2: Additional benefits of having N₂O on the unit is the added benefit of relief and relaxation during antepartum and post-partum procedures such as perineal repair, manual removal of placenta, and dilation and curettage.

Requirements: Patient Condition

1. Inclusion criteria:

- 1.1: 35 to 41 weeks gestational age
- 1.2: Singleton pregnancy
- 1.3: Spontaneous labor
- 1.4: Diet controlled gestational diabetes
- 1.5: Gestational thrombocytopenia
- 1.6: Fetus in vertex position
- 1.7: Planned for induction of labor
- 1.8: Oxygen saturation greater than or equal to 95% on room air
- 1.9: Have a Category I or II tracing

2. **Exclusion criteria:** (Collins, 2017; Collins, 2018; Collins et al., 2018; Likis et al., 2014).

- 2.1: History of pneumothorax, increased ocular pressure, intracranial pressure
- 2.2: Inner ear surgery
- 2.3: Low vitamin B12 (associated with celiac sprue disease),
- 2.4: Crohn's disease, pernicious anemia and gastric bypass surgery
- 2.5: History of alcohol or illegal drug use
- 2.6: Cannot hold her own mask

3. **General Guidelines:**

- 3.1: N2O can only be administered in the labor and delivery unit
- 3.2: N2O will be ordered by the physician or Certified Nurse Midwife (CNM) and initiated by the patient care registered nurse (RN), CNM, or obstetrician.
- 3.3: RN will provide initial and ongoing education. Education will include obtaining a proper seal by holding the mask over the nose and mouth and inhaling deeply. Inhaling provides negative pressure causing the demand valve to open permitting gas flow into the mask, exhaling releases the demand valve to close stopping the gas flow immediately.
- 3.4: Scavenger system will be kept/obtained in the medication prep room from the pyxis machine
- 3.5: Patient may not receive additional opioids while using N2O. Combination of opioids and N2O may result in respiratory depression, hypoxia, and unconsciousness.
- 3.6: If N2O is discontinued, ordered opioids and/or epidural may be given immediately without the need to consult with OB provider.
- 3.7: Only the patient will use N2O; therapy will terminate if there is misuse by visitors.
- 3.8: RN will stay at the bedside with initial administration of N2O and until the patient can demonstrate skill in use.

4. **Administration:**

- 4.1: Evaluate patient's response/coping mechanism to N₂O.
- 4.2: Instruct patient on self-management and placement of mask to make a seal, timing of breathing for maximum analgesic effect.

4.3: If anyone is observed using N₂O, they will be removed from the patient's room and N₂O therapy will terminate.

5. Procedure:

5.1: Treatment will stop upon patient's request or no longer needed.

5.2: Have patient grasp mask over nose and mouth to create a tight fit to open the flow of N₂O

5.3: Patient will begin to inhale deeply at the beginning of a contraction or right before a procedure to maximize effect and stop breathing in of N₂O when the contraction has surpassed the peak.

5.4: The patient will exhale N₂O directly into the mask so that the scavenger system will collect the N₂O rather than releasing it into room air.

5.5: The patient may take mask off when not contracting and breath normally.

6. On-going Assessment:

6.1: Evaluate maternal vital signs, oxygenation, and fetal heart rate pattern per unit protocol.

6.2: Assess for side effects such as dry mouth, drowsiness, dizziness, lightheaded, vertigo, orientation, dysphoria, amnesia, tingling of fingers and toes, nausea/vomiting.

7. Termination of Treatment:

7.1: Treatment and medication use is patient driven and can be discontinued at her discretion.

7.2: Discontinue use if any opposing effects of noncompliance, violence, alteration in vital signs, oxygen saturation, and ominous fetal tracing, or alteration in level of awareness

8. Documentation:

8.1: When N₂O was initiated and terminated in the nursing flowsheet in Health Connect.

8.2: Effectiveness of N₂O; pain management/satisfaction in the nursing flowsheet in Health Connect.

8.3: Complications and/or side effects

9. Care and storage of equipment:

9.1: Clean N₂O apparatus per manufacturer's instructions after each use.

9.2: Change disposable one-use face mask and tubing with each use.